

MESHGEL: AN EXPLORATORY SOLUTION OF SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP TO INFORMAL SETTLEMENTS

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Abstract:

Informal settlements have been a major concern for many countries around the world. Such unorganized regions of inhabitants are usually low on planned infrastructure and amenities. In countries with unemployment problems, the issue of informal settlements can be addressed along with unemployment and solved together through social entrepreneurship by collaborating with corporate partners. MESHGEL (matching education with skills, human resources, and goals of economic longevity) is a training and employment unit that can be replicated around these underprivileged areas to help in development and in reducing unemployment.

Key Words: Unemployment, Informal Settlements, Economic Development, Education & Training

Executive Summary:

Informal settlements can be tackled along with unemployment problems in many developing countries. Through collaborating with corporate partners, MESHGEL (Matching Education with Skills, Human resources, and Goals of Economic Longevity) is a training and employment unit that can be the proposed solution. This project of social entrepreneurship is planned in relationship to the Egypt, but it can be replicated in countries with a similar problem.

In order to address market needs and achieve lasting social impact on the development of Egypt and other countries, this project attempts to match partners from the corporate world with untrained workforce in underdeveloped regions and informal settlements. Corporate industries will set a unit called MESHGEL in an underprivileged neighborhood. The industry will provide basic trainings to workers in the region and hire them in these units with reasonable wages. Part of the profit made in these manufacturing units will go to the corporation and a percentage will remain for the expansion and sustainability of the MESHGEL. Later stages of the project are to include an Infirmary and a MESHGEL Junior Annex that would provide basic training and education for the homeless children of these regions.

The project can begin as a separate NGO or as a program in an existing NGO or a governmental institution. The project would ideally work as collaborative work between the Ministry of higher education and the Ministry of Urban Renewal and Informal Settlements. The project's business model assumes an ease of entry, sustainability and scalability. Its social impact extends to serve not only the unemployed workers, but also the unemployed university graduates, the homeless children and the partnering corporations. The long-term impact aspires to change the ecosystem of both these underdeveloped areas as well as the public/private partnerships in the field of education and development.

Introduction:

Recent changes in Egypt avow to the country's need for change. Unemployability has been one of the driving factors behind the socio-economic frustration building up and leading to the 25th January Revolution in 2011 and the ensuing unrest. Egypt is a country with great human resources, but many are neither trained nor have the necessary skills for the industry. The country has been suffering from two main problems: unemployment of university graduates, and multiplication of informal settlements. MESHGEL (Matching Education with Skills, Human resources, and Goals of Economic Longevity) is a training and employment unit that can be established in many informal settlements. The word "mesh gel" in Arabic means workshop. The idea of this project is to build one of these institutions, a "mesh gel", by one of the neighboring partnering corporations in underdeveloped districts or informal settlements so that the residents get technical training and other benefits. Now is a great time to incorporate such project especially due to current President's, El-Sisi's, attention to informal settlement by inaugurating the new Ministry for Urban Development and Informal Settlements; in addition to the interest in educational reform, development and projects in the Ministry of Higher Education in Egypt.

Context/Background:

Before the 2011 uprising, Egypt's real GDP growth, inflation and poverty levels have been impacted. A percentage of 18% of the Egyptian population lives below the national poverty line, and up to 40% in rural Upper Egypt. "Indeed, the partial modernization of Egypt's economy did not succeed in reaching a critical mass of its citizens" (World Bank, *Egypt: Country Brief*2011). In addition, one of the contributing factors to economic hardships and unemployability is Egypt's failing educational system, which had provided free public education for all since the 1950s. The public educational system has produced an inflated number of university graduates who are still unprepared for the market's technical and language skills. World Bank statistics maintain

that unemployment has risen in Egypt to 9.4%. Another hurdle facing Egyptian education and affecting its economy is the negative outlook towards vocational education and the scarcity of public/private partnerships between the educational sector, the industry and the government (a cooperation, otherwise known as the Triple Helix).

Market Overview:

Egypt is a large country, with a population of almost 80 million. The government has been working towards institutionalizing Public-private partnerships (PPPs) in many infrastructure projects (*Doing Business in Egypt* 2010: 2). Some NGOs, such as World Education Egypt, prefer to work directly within basic, primary and preparatory schools in Egypt, with special focus on girl education. Other NGOs, such as the Arab Alliance for Women (AAW) had micro projects financed by the Rotary Club movement in 2005 to provide women in the Houtaya slum in Giza with trainings and jobs. Many other sporadic projects have been undertaken by NGOs, the USAID and the World Bank to empower Egypt's youth or enhance Higher Education's impact by addressing the gap between its graduate outputs and the labor market needs (*The World Bank/OECD, A Review of Egypt's Higher Education*). As for the problem of informal settlements, a few NGOs are working on this problem; these include Ma'an for Developing Slums, trying to provide better dwellings in Ma3an City; in addition to other project by AUC in Ezbet el-Haggana and by GIZ in Manshiat Nasser.

Recently, and after Egypt's 2011 crisis, the World Bank Group, along with other partners, such as The African Development Bank, European Investment Bank, European Commission and the United States Agency for International Development (USAID) are committed to supporting the Egyptian people with a portfolio that includes 17 projects from the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (IBRD), in several sectors and with a total of \$3,765 million. Specifically, the IBRD Skill Development Project has trained 22,000 workers in 800 Egyptian enterprises (*World Bank, Egypt: Country Brief* 2011). Most active World Bank projects now either deal with the training of youth, the enhancement of curriculum or early childhood education enhancement (*World Bank, Egypt: Active Projects* 2011). These will all have an impact in the future.

However, the researcher is not aware of a program that seeks to partner with the corporate world in order to jointly address –and “on location”-- the existing unemployment of workers, that of university graduates, along with the basic education of homeless drop-out children; all leading to slum development.

Description/ Project Outline:

MESHGEL will encourage corporate industries to set a MESHGEL unit in a neighboring under developed region. The corporation will design the unit to produce its basic products, be that in textile, toys, garments, or electronics. After providing basic trainings to workers in the identified district (in collaboration between the MESHGEL management and the corporate partner), they will be employed in these units with reasonable salaries (but still cheap labor) and with health insurance. Part of the profit made in these manufacturing units will go to the corporation and a percentage will remain for the expansion and sustainability of the MESHGEL. Later stages of the project will include an Infirmary (Health clinic for the workers) and a MESHGEL Junior Annex that would provide basic training, education and sustenance for the homeless children of these regions.

Mission, Gap and Opportunity:

The Mission of this venture is: providing technical trainings and employment opportunities both to university graduates and workers of the MESHGEL districts through partnerships with corporations that agree to set up these workshops in underprivileged districts. The goals (both short- and long-term) thus include: (1) employment for university graduates as MASHGEL administrators, social workers, trainers, supervisors, or doctors and nurses (in the infirmaries); (2) technical daily jobs for regional labor force; (3) MESHGEL junior annex for basic education and trainings of drop-out and homeless children; (4) corporations can invest in these districts and both get labor and contribute to community development; (5) long-term goal: eradication of unemployment and child homelessness in MESHGEL regions.

This project has identified a gap in the educational system, pertaining to a mismatch between educational output and labor market needs. There is an unemployability because of the lack of skills both on the vocational level and of the tertiary education graduates, and there is a percentage of child drop-out of basic education in the slums. So, as part of social entrepreneurship, there is recognition of unjust equilibrium, then an opportunity, and finding a new equilibrium (Martin 2007). The mission succeeds in focusing upon opportunities and matching competencies (Dees 2001: 25). For example, opportunity is assessed through social value potential (mission-aligned and achievable outcomes), market potential (user-need and funder-interest) and sustainability potential (start-up and cost/benefit ratio) (Dees 2001: 53-54).

Theory of Change and Logical Framework:

This project's Theory of Change assumes that when the workforce of underdeveloped districts receives technical trainings in regional workshops in order to meet the specific needs of an industry, the companies will get their inexpensive human resource, the unemployed will secure jobs, and their communities will develop in the long run. This Theory of Change is delineated (as per Exhibit 1) in a logical framework, whereby the inputs include the laborers and university graduates who were underprivileged by not finding an opportunity for

employment, (for phase II there are also the drop-out homeless children that can get basic education and training in a later stage of the project), and the partnering corporations which will provide trainings and employment opportunities. The activities include technical trainings, skill development workshops and administrative job orientations. The output would be that the workers and university graduates become qualified for employment, whereas the partnering corporations find cheap trained human resource. In terms of outcomes, and on the medium term, the laborers and employees acquire technical skills, while the industry gets to expand and find workforce. As for the impact --i.e., the long-term effect on the society-- this entails finding links between educational outcomes and the market, community development, and working towards solving unemployment and child drop-outs and homelessness.

Business Model:

The model for MESHGEL is a non-profit¹ organization built on public/private partnerships. In this case the type of partnership is to provide both professional and educational services.² The business model of any organization is its operating model and planning tool. Business planning “is an important tool for organizations developing and scaling solutions to social problems and for the organizations that invest in them” (Wolk and Kreitz 2008: 3). It can help (1) identify opportunities, (2) develop innovations, (3) demonstrate accountability, and (4) achieve financial sustainability (Wolk and Kreitz. 2008: 2). For the purpose of this analysis, a business model made of 9 building blocks will be used (as per Exhibit 2).

If we begin by looking at (1) the customer segment, we realize that MESHGEL serves both the workers and university graduates by providing them with the necessary skills, and the corporate world by providing them with the future trained human resource. (2) The customer relationships include the public-private partnership, as well as MESHGEL’s relationship to both the employee and the corporate world. (3) The value proposition would be that MESHGEL participates in training skillful human resources and matching them with employment opportunities. (4) These values can be achieved through a set of activities such as performing the needs analyses of the corporations, designing trainings for the workers with the help of the corporate partners, and putting together quick orientations for university graduates who will work as administrators. (5) Some of their key resources depend on the corporate volunteers and their funding; others will be generated from the profits of each unit. (6) The model entails a few possible³key partners, such as Sawiris, Shell, or Sekem; as well as International NGOs, such as USAID, World Education, etc. (7) The distribution channels include volunteer advocates in local districts and universities, as well as the use of the Internet or other social media. (8) The revenue streams, or what the customers are willing to pay, include funding from the corporations, and time and effort from the workers and university graduates. Finally, (9) some of the cost structure can be outlined as: facilities, technology, materials, program expenses and salaries.

Social Impact Model:

The Social Impact Model connects the social problem to: (1) the mission, (2) the approach, (3) the strategies, (4) the impact, and (5) the vision of success (Wolk and Kreitz 2008: 15). As per Exhibit 3, the Social Impact Model begins by the Social Problem Definition that attempts to identify the problem, define the needs and opportunities (possibly by needs and opportunity analyses), and frame a unique approach. MESHGEL’s problem definition can be considered the unemployment problem and the gap or mismatch between education and skills among the youth. The needs analysis will be based on the identified skills needed by the partnering corporations. The Mission has included the beneficiaries, activities and expected outcomes. These have all been previously outlined for MESHGEL in the logical framework. They also overlap with the Social Impact Strategies that are equivalent to the major activities in the logical framework. The Organization and Performance Indicators are equivalent to the outputs in the logical framework; and need to abide by a certain measure of accountability (that will be outlined in the performance measurement section). The Social and Economic Impact Indicators can also be referred to as the outcomes in the logical framework. They need be SMART: Specific, Measurable, Action-oriented, Realistic and Timed. They will need “some measurement methodologies” (Wolk and Kreitz 2008: 19). If we move to the Operating Model, it means the way to go about achieving the vision; or in other words it is the Business Model (as previously outlined). The Vision of Success is what the research assumes will work and what the long-term goal is. MESHGEL’s vision of success assumes that by collaborating with the corporate world to provide trainings and jobs in manufacturing units, the gap between educational outputs and market needs can be filled, contributing to solve unemployability and to the development of the selected regions. Finally, the Feedback Loop is a measure of self-evaluation and can be considered as part of accountability.

Implementation Strategy:

MESHGEL’s implementation strategy includes the timeline, phases and strategy goals, and the organizational capacity:(a) team, (b) governance, (c) financial sustainability, (d) marketing, (e) technology, (f) public policy, (g) performance and social impact measurement, (h) risk mitigation, and (i) action plan.

¹With the possibility of growing into a hybrid non-profit venture, according to the model described by Elkington and Hartigan (2008: 37).

² Other partnerships could be for management, support, or operational services; as well as facility availability (Patrinos et al. 2009: 9-14).

³ Since this start-up is still a proposal, none of these potential partners have been approached yet.

I. Timeline:

The project timeline will follow a short start-up phase, or a phase in which to be incubated by another NGO or incorporated into a governmental institution, in order to establish the organization/project and to make connections, then it will attempt to explore the prospects with a pilot program partnering with, for example, the textile industry. Following, there could be a third phase whereby the complementary vision of the project expands deep by implementing the programs of the Junior Annex and the Infirmary. The main focus of these two stages would be that job opportunities are given to residents of these regions since the whole social impact was to raise their standard of living and develop their districts.

II. Phases/Goals (Growth Strategy):

The project will assume five phases (as per Exhibit 4).

Phase 1: Initial Preparations and Establishment of Operations: This phase will last for 6 months. During this period there will be an attempt to recognize the NGO as an Egyptian/international non-profit, or incorporate the project into a governmental institution. Also, the services of an IT specialist may be solicited to design a website. This time will also be used to establish a network with donors and corporate partners, to undertake the necessary research to both identify the corporate needs, as well as to research the potential underdeveloped regions or informal settlements with the following characteristic: proximity to corporate partners, a reasonable number of unemployed workers and college graduates, and few homeless children. A researcher and a donor outreach operator may need to be employed. In this first phase, trainings can be developed and by the end, performance and key success factors will be assessed.

Phase 2: Pilot Program in Five Regions in Greater Cairo: The second phase is assigned one year, in order to undertake a pilot project. The pilot project will focus on partnering with textile corporations in 5 different underdeveloped regions in Greater Cairo. The reason behind the focus on this particular industry for Egypt pertains to Egypt's historical reputation in the cotton industry as well as its competitively cheap labor. Despite all that, the country has not been able to live to its potential in the textile industry. "Ready-made garment production has the potential not just to fuel export revenues, but also to help maintain and increase mass employment" (Wasser 2009). That is, such sector can open up ample employment opportunities. For example, Arafa Holding, which is a manufacturer known for exporting designer garments, can be approached for partnership in order to inaugurate several MESHGEL units in neighbors with proximity to the company's manufacturing premises in the City of 10th of Ramadan (part of Greater Cairo). The research will expose whether it is suitable to take up regions in the City of 10th of Ramadan, or in the neighboring Al-Salam City. By the end of this phase, the organization will need to assess its performance, determine key success factors, and design improvements based on lessons learnt.

Phase 3: Scaling-deep through Expansion of Services: This phase will attempt to extend the services to the homeless children through the Junior Annex program and to improve health services in the region through the Infirmary program. The phase is expected to take one year.

Phase 4: Scaling Horizontally and Covering Various Egyptian Governorates: This stage attempts to reach beyond greater Cairo to the rest of the Egyptian governorates. In a period of five years, reasonable market saturation is projected. This first requires that MESHGEL has the 5 Rs: readiness, receptivity, resources, risks and returns (Dees 2004: 30). Defining the innovation is also important for going to scale. In order to lead sustainable and scalable organizations, certain strategies can be employed; for example, democratizing technology, changing the system (towards more transparency and accountability), and scaling solutions (Elkington and Hartigan 2008: 204).

Phase 5: Changing the Eco-system: Going to Africa and the Developing World: This phase explores the replicability of the model beyond the Egyptian context to similar contexts in the developing world. A five-year timeline is expected for each country. The model can be attempted in several countries simultaneously. This means the easiness of its entry, or its replicability and scalability. By seeking more PPP, it can also be easily scalable within the different regions in Egypt or any underdeveloped region in the developing or developed world; it would then become disruptive to the ecosystem.

III. Organizational Capacity:

- (a) **Team and Governance:** Presently in this conceptualizing stage, the project has its Founder and President who has experience in education and public administration. During Phase I, the team will need to recruit a market researcher and a funding outreach officer. In phase II, the project will launch its five units, which will start employing university graduates as administrators and supervisors. At this second stage, there will be need for a human resource director as well as a project manager. As phases expand, more staff will be needed.
- (b) **Financial Sustainability:** In terms of capitalization, it means identifying the amount needed by venture philanthropists, by subtracting the expenses from the already acquired revenues. The seed funding is also expected to be from philanthropist international organizations. The start-up budget is supposed to be covered by such philanthropist NGOs and it includes Phase one, or the first 6 months. The expenses include the market research and the web design.

As for financial sustainability, it is assumed within this business model. First, the major part of the financial cost will be mainly covered by the corporate partners who should get a positive Return on Investment (ROI) from the manufacturing unit, the MESHGEL. The model is designed as a for-profit model, but with a not-for-profit identity. A percentage of the profit will be assigned to the MESHGEL units and the expansion of the project. It is thus designed for sustainability.

- (c) **Marketing:** There has to be standards and systems to communicate, in a capturing way, what the organization does to reach whoever will help increase the impact. “These groups include the beneficiaries of your programs, or your target markets, and potential partners-including social impact investors, local decision makers, and leaders of peer organizations” (Wolk and Kreitz 2008: 37). That is, accordingly, marketing can be divided into three parts: (a) brand and communications, (b) target marketing, and (c) partnerships (Wolk: 37). For brand and communications, it is possible to begin with an audit to approaching how to communicate social impact to the stakeholders. The writer of this project recognizes three major stakeholders, as target market as well as potential partnerships. First, the beneficiaries in the underprivileged regions. They will need direct communication and a team that interacts with them personally to market the goals of the project. They can also be reached through media coverage, especially T.V. programs. Second, there are the social impact foundations, such as the USAID, World Bank, UNDP, Sawiris Foundation for Social Development, Save the Children, Injaz, AIC, or World Education. For them, reference to Millennium Development Goals of basic education for all children, (thus including drop-outs), can play an attractive marketing strategy. They can be reached by proposals, a sound “elevator pitch”, and an attractive website. Third, there are the corporate partners –such as Arafa Holding, Orascom or Shell Egypt-- who can be allured by brochures emphasizing their role as part of Corporate Social Responsibility, as well as the potential for financial profitability for them.
- (d) **Technology:** Though the project is low tech (will only need computers for data entry and measurement systems), the plan recognizes technology’s importance in expanding, especially as the project starts providing basic education for homeless children and literacy programs for the workers. Technology is important for scale. Also, the “right technology can greatly increase your organizational capacity, while enhancing your ability to serve you target population, to connect with other stakeholders, and to demonstrate your organization’s impact with the data you collect over time” (Wolk and Kreitz 2008: 42).
- (e) **Public Policy:** For something to be a social movement, you have to change the mindset of the people, put pressure on the existing system and challenge the status quo. One needs to identify the policy makers and approach them. It is important to be aware of the national policies and legalization. Public policy is specifically important for “large-scale social impact” (Wolk and Kreitz 2008: 43). Thinking of the key players includes knowing the legalization process which in the end recognizes the organization as an NGO. A decision will have to be made somewhere along the road about whether it is better for such NGO to be local or international, and whether to start as a separate entity or to partner with an existing NGO. Also, for scaling, it could be crucial to seek the assistance of governmental bodies such as the Ministry of Social Solidarity and Justice, the Ministry of Education, the Ministry of Higher Education, the Ministry for Urban Renewal and Informal Settlements, the Ministry of Industry and Trade and the Ministry of Local Development. There needs to be collaboration, which can be done if one of the funding parties is a recognized entity such as the World Bank, the USAID or the European Union.
- (f) **Performance and Social Impact:** It is important to recognize what would be the Metrics for Success. There has to be a strategy to make performance management easier and become accountable to all stakeholders (Ebrahim 2010: 2). According to Ebrahim, there needs to be accountability in finance, governance, performance and mission. Measurement will thus be for clarity of goals, priorities, standards and feedback. It will, however, be taken into consideration not to be too restricting. As part of self-evaluation, MESHGEL will want to develop indicators to assess its performance and make improvements. For example, there will be Program Performance Indicators, using Balanced Scorecards to assess the administrative performance. There will also be Outreach Indicators, for the number of partners, beneficiaries or market targets approached. Dashboards and report cards will be used for quick data analysis and are specially a valid component in the feedback loop. Financial and governance transparency will be maintained by publishing financial reports and Board governing bodies on the web. A research agenda can also be engrained from the beginning for its importance in impact measurement.
- (g) **Risk Mitigation:** For any project there are political, ethical and economic risks. Politically, the country has been through a period of civil unrest. Ethically, there may be reservations and criticism about labor regulations and child labor. Economically and in terms of doing business, the corporate partners may be reluctant to invest in something that has not proven successful yet. International investors may also

be dissuaded by the fear of corruption and lack of transparency; since Egypt ranked 111 out of 180 country in Transparency International's Global Corruption Perception index in 2009 (*Doing Business*: 3).

In order to mitigate these risks: politically, despite the unrest, the new leadership may be willing to try new initiatives that push towards economic development. The government buy-in may be important and can be supported through community outreach. Ethically, the whole idea of the project is to serve, not abuse, the underprivileged. Homeless children will be trained and provided with basic education and training instead of being left to beg in the streets. The NGO will also comply with both regional and international laws about child labor and minimum wages for adult laborers. Economically, the local partners are already investing in Egypt. This project is nothing but an expansion of their businesses as well as a chance to exercise Corporate Social Responsibility. As for the international funders, transparency and accountability measures will be reinforced to provide assurances. The project will also begin on a small scale until its success proven.

IV. Action Plan:

For the 6 months of phase I, the action plan attempts to outline the goals and their possible timeline. The main goals are in the set-up stage and include: (a) Start informal communication with corporate partners; (b) Finalize business plan; (c) Send the business plan to potential Angel Investors; (d) Design and refine the website; (e) Begin market research and district selection; (f) Solicit contact with government officials and policy makers; (g) Begin process legalization.

Challenges and Model Adequacy:

The challenges facing MESHGEL are (1) finding partners and angel investors; (2) managing a large number of workers; (3) maintaining a balance between profitability for the corporate partners (and sustainability for the organization) with the attempted social impact; (4) maintaining a balance between child training and avoiding its negative connotations with child labor; (5) starting with a large scale plan from scratch; (6) maintaining sustainability and profitability to hold onto the corporate partners; (7) engraving in the beneficiaries a culture of commitment and punctuality; (8) working towards education and slum development at the same time. The Model adequacy is designed to address such challenges, but will require a lot of hard work. For instance, for MESHGEL to attract more international philanthropic organizations, it will maintain financial transparency on its website and publish its financial reports. It will also need to maintain its accountability for the stakeholders --with clear performance measurement systems. The quasi for-profit model is designed to maintain profitability for the corporate partners as well as sustainability for MESHGEL. The model is designed like a win-for-all solution; so, it will be in the interest of all involved parties to see it succeed. All in all, the idea is both simple in essence, but large in scale, application and impact. Its success can change the ecosystem in not only education but economic development as well. In short, MESHGEL (Matching Education with Skills, Human resources, and Goals of Economic Longevity) is a training and employment unit that can be replicated around underprivileged areas, using social entrepreneurship by collaborating with corporate partners, to help solve the issue of informal settlements along with unemployment.

References:

1. Dees, A. and Wei-skilern. 2004. *Scaling Social Impact*. Stanford: Stanford Social Innovation Review.
2. Dees, G., Jed E. and Peter E. 2001. *Enterprising Nonprofits*. NY: John Wiley & Sons.
3. *Doing Business in Egypt: 2010 Country Commercial Guide for U.S. Companies*. 2010. U.S. Commercial Services. <<http://www.buyusa.gov/egypt/en/doingbusinessinegypt.html>>.
4. Ebrahim, Alnoor and Kasturi Rangan. 2010. *The Limits of Nonprofit Impact*. Boston: Harvard Business School.
5. Elkington and Hartigan. 2008. *The Power of Unreasonable People*. Boston: Harvard Business Press.
6. IRIN Middle East. 2005. *Egypt: Local focus pays off for NGO helping slum women to earn cash*. <<http://www.irinnews.org/Report.aspx?ReportID=25593>>.
7. Kellogg Foundation. *Logic Model Development Guide*. 2001. Michigan: W.K. Kellogg Foundation.
8. Martin, Roger and Sally Osberg. 2007. "Social Entrepreneurship: The Case for Definition." *Stanford Social Innovation Review*.
9. Patrinos et al. 2009. *The Role and Impact of Public-Private Partnerships in Education*. The World Bank.
10. Wasser, Louis. 2009. "Garment Game." *American Chamber of Commerce in Egypt*. <http://www.amcham.org.eg/resources_publications/publications/business_monthly/issue.asp?sec=5&im=7&iy=2009>.
11. World Bank. 2011. *Egypt: Active Projects*. <<http://web.worldbank.org/external/default/main?menuPK=287189&pagePK=141143&piPK=141103&theSitePK=256307>>.
12. World Bank. 2011. *Egypt: Country Brief*. <<http://web.worldbank.org/wbsite/external/countries/menaext/egyptextn/0,, menuPK:287166~pagePK:141132~piPK:141107~theSitePK:256307,00.html>>.

13. World Bank. 2010. Egypt: A Review of Egypt’s Higher Education.<<http://web.worldbank.org/wbsite/external/countries/menaext/egyptextn/0,,contentMDK:22526554~menuPK:287175~pagePK:2865066~piPK:2865079~theSitePK:256307,00.html>>.
14. World Education Egypt. 2011. “Past Projects.” World education Egypt. <http://egypt.worlded.org/past_projects.htm>.
15. Wolk and Kreitz. 2008. Business Planning for Enduring Social Impact. Cambridge: Rootcause.

Exhibit 1:

MESHGEL

Logical Framework⁴

Exhibit 2:

MESHGEL

Business Model Canvas⁵

<p>Key Partners *Possible Corporate partners (such as Sawiris, Shell, Nokia, Sekem, Arafa Holding, etc). * Possible International NGOs (such as USAID, World Education, Save the Children, Injaz, etc).</p>	<p>Key Activities * Performing the needs analyses of the corporations. * Designing trainings for the workers. * Designing Orientations for the administrators. * Designing Education programs and trainings for the homeless child. * Launching health services for the employed and district.</p>	<p>Value Proposition * Employment for all. * Skillful human resources. * Saving the homeless kid.</p>	<p>Customer Relationships Collaboration between customer segments, mediated by MESHGEL</p>	<p>Customer Segments * District workers. * District university graduates. * District homeless children. * Regional corporate partners.</p>
	<p>Key Resources * Profits. * Funding.</p>		<p>Distribution Channels * Volunteerism in local districts and universities. * Local NGOs. * Internet and social media.</p>	

⁴ Based on the Logic Model Development Guide. Michigan: W.K. Kellogg Foundation, 2001.

⁵ This specific business model is based on class notes and Mariano Batalla’s presentation at Harvard.

<p>Cost Structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Facilities * Salaries * Materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Program expenses * Technology 	<p>Revenue Streams</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Customers are willing to work (youth and workers) and put and get fund (corporations)
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Exhibit 3:

MESHGEL

**Social Impact Model⁶
Data**

Feedback Loop

Exhibit 4:

MESHGEL

Operations/ Timeline

Phase 1: (Start-up) (6 Months)	Initial Preparations and Establishment of Operations
Phase 2: (One Year)	Pilot Program in Five Regions in Greater Cairo
Phase 3: (One Year)	Scaling-deep through Expansion of Service Offerings: Junior Annex and Health Services
Phase 4: (Five Years)	Scaling Horizontally and Covering Various Egyptian Governorates
Phase 5: (Five Years)	Changing the Eco-system: Going to Africa and the Developing World

⁶From Wolk and Kreitz. Business Planning for Enduring Social Impact.